

CHEMISTRY TEACHERS' AND STUDENTS' PERCEPTION OF PROBLEMS OF LEARNING CHEMISTRY IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OGBIA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE

BY

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Abstract

This study investigated chemistry teachers and students' perception of problems of learning chemistry in senior schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised all the 5185 senior schools' students in Ogbia Local Government Area Bayelsa State. Random sampling technique was used to select the number of schools while purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample size of one hundred and thirty-three (133) students and fourteen (14) teachers drawn from 7 selected senior schools in Ogbia LGA. A researcher made questionnaire titled, "Chemistry Teachers' Perception of Problem of Learning Chemistry in Senior Schools (CTPPLCSS) and Students' Perception of Problem of Learning Chemistry in Senior Schools (SPPLCSS)" were used as instruments for data collection for the study. Two research questions were formulated to guide the study. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha formula and coefficients of 0.9 and 0.9 were obtained. Data were analyzed using tables, mean and standard deviation. Results revealed disturbing teachers and students' perception of learning chemistry to include absenteeism to class, language of science, poor teachers' welfare, among others. This implied that use of innovative methods in teaching chemistry would help mitigate language gap that enhance difficulty of the subject. It was recommended that attention should be paid to use of appropriate teaching methods, instructional materials, teachers' welfare and capacity building through training programmes to enhance performance and ensure quality delivery.

Keywords: Chemistry Education, Learning, Perception, Problem, Students, Teachers

Introduction

Education is a major tool needed for advancement of nations. It is the strongest instrument for imparting knowledge, attitudes, skills and habits into the younger generation from time to time. It is the driver that communicates knowledge, skills, capacities and competence to the learners in order to live responsibly and contribute to growth of society in which they belong and science education remains one of the viable solutions to driving home these skills for sustainability and national development (FRN, 2013). Science education is a special component of education that should be handled by teachers with relevant skills, training and educational qualification because it is the

integration of teaching method with the study of physics, chemistry, biology and other science subjects in the faculty of education. It becomes a disarray when these science subjects are handled by teachers with little or no skills, training and competence in teaching methods. No wonder the outcome and quality of teachers in our schools today (Etebu and Amatori, 2020).

Latest research has shown that some of the approaches used in teaching science and chemistry in particular in Nigerian secondary schools do not yield best results (Oladejo et al., 2021). Teaching and learning of science in the secondary schools has not been satisfactory as the chalk and talk approach which is heavily tilted towards rote

learning, teacher centered and examination focus while neglecting practical activity approaches that improve teaching and learning is still prevalent today (Okebukola, 2020; Oladejo et al., 2021). The traditional method discourages students from active engagement and heightens memorization of facts and perceptions of science being abstract among students.

Science is pivotal in technological advancement that have great impact in man's existence and national development. Perhaps, this contributed to its global and national recognition that led the Federal Government of Nigeria to introduce the 6-3-3-4 system of education in the country and the compulsory teaching of science and technology at senior secondary schools (FRN, 2014). This birthed the policy that at least one of the three science subjects Physics, Chemistry and Biology be taught as core subjects in the senior schools and the reference that 60% of the intakes into the universities be in science and science related areas (FRN, 2014). The significance of chemistry in education, health, agriculture, biology and engineering among others is huge and cannot be ignored and as such be handled with utmost care in teaching and learning in senior schools. Chemistry is a natural science that explains structure and composition of elements, atoms, molecules and ions (Brown 2018). It remains one of the requirements for taking a science oriented course in higher education.

Egolum and Ekene (2020) opined that high failure rate in chemistry is as a result of factors such as lack of functional laboratory, other science facilities, foundation knowledge of mathematical concepts, qualified science teachers, teaching methods, students perception of chemistry, teaching methods and heavy curriculum. Shoge & Kabiru (2024) stated that causes of students' poor performance include inadequate laboratory facilities, limited time for conducting practical, teachers' attitude, over loaded syllabus, student perception and attitude, examination malpractice, class size, among others. Studies hold that the poor performance in chemistry is also caused by students learning attitude, gender bias, inappropriate use of teaching aids and teaching methods (Musengimana et al., 2021; Oladayo,

2024) The study of Surya & Arty (2021), also confirmed that poor performance of students is as a result of lack interest in chemistry as a subject and female show more interest in chemistry than male. Students interest has continuously decrease in learning science, chemistry in particular, as they move from lower classes to higher classes, which is a red flag to advancement of science, technology and national development (Musengimana et al, 2021). Amazingly, only less than 50% of a respondent population under study were able to take employment that required knowledge and skill in chemistry (Nidup et al., 2021). Also, stakeholders in education, understanding of learners view about chemistry education is crucial to finding solution to poor academic performance of students in chemistry. This study therefore sought to find out teachers and students' perception of the problems of teaching chemistry in senior schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

According to Shoge and Kabiru (2024) investigated the perception of students' interest towards learning chemistry at senior secondary school. A descriptive research design was adopted in this study. Convenient sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 50 students from five different schools of the study were used in the study. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire containing 10 items. Result revealed that most of the students do not relate chemistry concepts with their everyday lifestyle. Also, students had difficulty to understand chemistry lessons due to inadequate resources in teaching and learning chemistry. The study recommended that attention should be given to schools to improve on attitudes, interests and perceptions of students toward Chemistry.

Egolum and Okonkwo, (2022) investigated perception of chemistry teachers on secondary school chemistry curriculum in terms of its content: need for its reform. The study chose a descriptive design survey for the study. 4 research questions were raised to guide the study. 148 chemistry teachers were randomly sampled from 86 senior schools from 229 public schools in Anambra state as sample for the study. The study used a researcher made questionnaire for data collection and a

reliability index of 0.89 using Cronbach Alpha computation. Mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentages were used to answer the research question. Findings revealed that chemistry curriculum used in secondary schools is heavy with contents that cannot be covered within the term and some topics are so abstract for the students understanding. Recommendation included chemistry contents should be relevant, practical and relatable in order to inculcate knowledge, skills and attitude to the students.

Naeem, Ali and Ahmad (2022) investigated evaluation of the causes of interest decline in the subject of chemistry amongst higher secondary school students in Karachi Pakistan. Descriptive research design was employed in the study. All the higher education students in private institute of Karachi East formed the population of the study. Convenient sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 450 students from the population. Interview and a 31 item researcher made structured questionnaire were used to collection for the study. Descriptive analysis was done using mean, standard deviation and SPSS. Findings showed that IUPAC and equation names make students to struggle in second year. Also, only 10 students that were interviewed had chemistry as favorite. Reaction mechanism, atomic structure, electron location and orbital forms are imaginary and difficult to understand. This implied that as students interest decrease, the subject chemistry became more difficult to them.

The study recommended audio-visual tools for conceptual learning, training and retraining of chemistry teachers to improve students' interest in chemistry. Nidup, Zangmo, Rinzin, Yuden, Subba, and Rai (2021) investigated perception of class X students of phuentsholing higher secondary school towards chemistry in Bhutan. A descriptive research design was used for the study. For this research, 90 students were chosen A sample size of 90 was selected from a population of 95 students using convenience sampling technique to maintain 95% confidence level and 0.025 margin of error. Cronbach's alpha was used to calculate the reliability index of 0.89. A researcher made survey questionnaire comprised of 41 items was used for collection of data. Descriptive analysis was carried

out with excel/SPSS. Results show that chemistry is least liked students' subject. Although, students learn more during practical but do not find practical enjoyable and fun. Abstract nature of chemistry and chemical formulae make learning difficult to students. Results also noted that multimedia were not maximally used in teaching.

Shidiq, Permanasari and Hernani (2020) investigated chemistry teacher's perception towards STEM learning. The study employed purposive-design survey method. 37 chemistry teachers participated in the study. A random sampling was used and structured questionnaires were given to chemistry teachers from different level of education in central java and Indonesia. Results revealed that chemistry teachers had good perception of carrying out teaching and learning of chemistry using STEM approach as it could improve students' understanding and skills for emerging concerns in the 21st century.

The review showed an upward trend of poor academic performance in chemistry among chemistry students over the years. This report is in agreement of Chief Examiner's Report (WAEC, 2022). Studies also show that numerous factors contribute to difficulty in learning chemistry. Available literature show that students are experiencing challenges in academics, hence, trends of poor academic performance in chemistry education that necessitated the study. Literature available are done in other locations, hence, the population gap of the study. It is on this note that the study sought to investigate chemistry teachers and students' perception of problems of learning chemistry in senior schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry education is pivotal in sustainable development in any nation today. It has contributed to acquisition of knowledge, skills and attitude for preparation for life after school. It is commonly found problematic and chemistry students eventually develop a wide range of alternative conceptions (Egolum & Ekene, 2020). Numerous research reports expressed that the difficulties in Chemistry arise from the abstract, complex and dynamic nature of the concepts covered, heavily

loaded course content, teacher-centered teaching, erroneously constructed students' knowledge due to lack of clear vision, and lack of students' and teachers' motivation (Oladejo et al., 2021; Nidup et al., 2021). Chemistry teachers blamed students for scoring low grades in the subject and on the other hand, chemistry students blamed their teachers for inability to teach them well. Some studies found that the majority of chemistry teachers had a degree in a field other than chemistry, such as biology or mathematics and insufficient resources, such as textbooks, non functional laboratories, inadequate facilities and teachers' qualification also contribute to the problem (Musengimana et al., 2021; Oladayo, 2025). As a result, chemistry students are not able to perform well in external examinations, which has a negative impact on their future prospects. This gap has resulted to poor academic performance of chemistry students in external examination in secondary schools. Therefore, this study sought to investigate teachers and students' perception of the problems in teaching and learning of chemistry in secondary schools.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine teachers' and students' perception of problems of learning chemistry in senior secondary schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are teachers' perception of problems of learning chemistry in secondary schools?
2. What are students' perception of the problems of learning chemistry in secondary schools?

Research Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Descriptive survey research design is a design in which a group of people or item is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few individuals or items considered to be representatives of the entire group. The population comprised all the 34 senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area. Bayelsa State (Education Board). The number of chemistry teachers and senior secondary school 2 students in Ogbia Local Government Area is 34 and 5185 respectively. Purposive sampling technique was

adopted to determine the sample size of the study. The sample size consisted of 133 students and 14 teachers from 7 sampled schools from all the senior secondary schools in Ogbia LGA in Bayelsa State. This is a non-probability sampling technique which require the researcher to select respondents based on certain criteria. The selection was based on the use of intact classes, students choice of chemistry as a subject, students present in school, teachers present in school and the teachers are the respondents' teachers. The choice of the schools was based on the school having experienced chemistry teachers who had teaching qualification and willing to contribute in the study.

The choice of the location was based on good road network, which is motorable and not water transport as the terrain is riverine. A researcher designed questionnaire titled Chemistry Teachers' Perception of Problem of Learning Chemistry in Senior Schools (CTPPLCSS) and Students' Perception of Problem of Learning Chemistry in Senior Schools (SPPLCSS) were used as instruments for data collection. The experts in science education verified the instruments and the final draft was used for the study. The researchers went to the schools and administered the instruments to the respondents. The teachers' population was 4 males and 3 females. They had Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) and Bachelor of Science in Education (B.Sc (Ed). One-on-one mode of instrument administration was adopted in the study. The researchers visited the sampled schools and administered the instruments which were returned immediately after answering. This method ensured a 100% return rate. A pilot study on 20 respondents from 2 secondary schools that were not part of the study population was done and 0.9 index was achieved as reliability using Cronbach alpha calculation. Research questions were answered using tables, mean and standard deviation and the mean scores of 2.50 and above were accepted while below mean scores of 2.50 were rejected. Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4 points, Agreed (A) = 3 points, Disagreed (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1 point were the weighted mean respectively. The summary of mean, variance, standard deviation and remarks of chemistry teachers' perception of problem of

learning chemistry in senior schools in Ogbia LGA shown in table 1 below.

Results

Table 1: Summary of mean, standard deviation and variance scores on the chemistry teachers’ perception of problem of learning chemistry in senior schools

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	SD ²	Remark
1	Absenteeism of students from school is one of the causes of failure in chemistry subject	3.5	1.71	2.93	A
2	Poor learning environment where there are no chairs and table for students contribute to poor performance in chemistry subject	3.4	1.63	2.67	A
3	Some grammar, language, concept used in chemistry textbook is difficult for students to understand	2.6	1.26	1.60	A
4	Lack of equipment in the laboratory in some schools’ hinder students to be taught practical aspect of chemistry	2.7	1.26	1.60	A
5	Grammar and language used in some chemistry textbooks cause confusion to students	2.6	1.26	1.60	A
6	Poverty is one of the causes of that lead to poor performance of students	2.2	1.31	1.73	R
7	Some chemistry textbook in library is outdated	3.2	1.51	2.27	A
8	Some chemistry teachers’ attitude discouraged student to listen during teaching	1.9	1.46	2.13	R
9	Lack of specimens in laboratory contribute to poor performance in chemistry subject	2.5	1.26	1.60	A
10	Calculations in some topics in chemistry subjects isn’t well explained due to time	1.8	1.53	2.33	R
11	Time given to teach chemistry in class isn’t enough	2.0	1.41	2.00	R
12	Some chemistry teachers in secondary schools are not chemistry teacher by profession	2.2	1.32	1.73	R
13	Some diagram, structures, concept used in chemistry textbook is difficult for students to understand	1.9	1.46	2.13	R
14	Lack of infrastructure and modern facilities contributed to poor performance of students	2.4	1.26	1.60	R
15.	Some chemistry teachers teach in class without instructional materials which aid learning	2.0	1.41	2.00	R
16	Some schools don’t have laboratory to teach student practical aspect of the subject which is very crucial	3.4	1.63	2.67	A
17	Low salary paid to teachers didn’t encourage them to teach effectively	3.2	1.50	2.26	A
18	Inadequate chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools contribute to the failure of students in chemistry	2.5	1.26	1.60	A
19	Financial constraint of chemistry teachers did not encourage them to teach effectively	3.5	1.71	2.93	A
20	Absenteeism of some chemistry teachers which didn’t allow them to cover schedule syllabus contribute to failure of chemistry students	2.5	1.26	1.60	A
	Grand total	52	28.41		
	Grand Mean	2.60			

X = mean, SD = Standard Deviation, SD² = Variance, R = Rejected and A = Accepted

The summary of the result presented in table 4.1 shows the various problems associated with teachers’ perception of problem in chemistry. Items 1,2,3,4,5,7,9,16,17,18,19 and 20 has the

means scores of 2.5 and above, which is above the critical value of 2.5 showing they are the main problem associated with teachers’ perception of chemistry learning while items 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13,

14, and 15 shows the means score below 2.5 which is below the critical value which means that they are not the main problems of learning chemistry as perceived by chemistry teachers. Chemistry teachers' perception recorded a Grand mean score of 52 and standard deviation of 28.41. This

indicates that chemistry teachers' perception of the problem of chemistry learning has a negative impact on students' performance of chemistry in senior secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Areas.

Table 2: Summary of mean, standard deviation and variance scores on students' perception of the problem of learning chemistry in senior schools

S/N	ITEMS	X	SD	SD ²	Remark
1	Absenteeism of students from school is one of the causes of failure in chemistry subject	3.0	1.41	2.00	A
2	Poor learning environment where there is no chains and table for students contribute to poor performance in chemistry subject	3.1	1.46	2.13	A
3	Some grammar, language, concept used in chemistry textbook is difficult for students to understand	2.9	1.37	1.87	A
4	Lack of equipment is in laboratory in some schools hinder students to be trained practical aspect of chemistry	3.1	1.46	2.13	A
5	Grammar and language used in some chemistry textbooks cause confusion to students	2.7	1.26	1.60	A
6	Poverty is one of the causes of that lead to poor performance of students	2.8	1.31	1.73	A
7	Some chemistry textbook in library is outdated	2.9	1.37	1.87	A
8	Some chemistry teachers' attitude discouraged student to listen during teaching	2.8	1.32	1.73	A
9	Lack of specimens in laboratory contribute to poor performance in chemistry subject	3.2	1.53	2.33	A
10	Calculations in some topics in chemistry subjects isn't well explained due to time	2.9	1.37	1.87	A
11	Time given to teach chemistry in class isn't enough	2.6	1.26	1.60	A
12	Some chemistry teachers in secondary schools are not chemistry teacher by profession	3.0	1.41	2.00	A
13	Some diagram, structures, concept used in chemistry textbook is difficult for students to understand	2.6	1.26	1.60	A
14	Lack of infrastructure and modern facilities contributed to poor performance of students	2.9	1.37	1.87	A
15.	Some chemistry teachers teach in class without instructional materials which aid learning	2.8	1.32	1.73	A
16	Some schools don't have laboratory to teach student practical aspect of the subject which is very crucial	3.0	1.41	2.00	A
17	Low salary paid to teachers didn't encourage them to teach effectively	2.8	1.32	1.73	A
18	Inadequate chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools contribute to the failure of students in chemistry	2.8	1.32	1.73	A
19	Financial constraint of chemistry teachers did not encourage them to teach effectively	2.8	1.32	1.73	A
20	Absenteeism of some chemistry teachers which didn't allow them to cover schedule syllabus contribute to failure of chemistry students	3.1	1.46	2.13	A
	Grand Total	57.8	27.31		
	Grand Mean	2.89			

A = Accepted, R = Rejected, X = Mean, SD = Standard deviation and SD² = Variance

The summary of the result presented in table 2 show the various problems associated with

students' perception of problem in chemistry. Items by items analysis show the means score

below 2.6 to 3.1 which is above the critical value which mean that all the items were shown to be the main problem of learning as perceived by chemistry students. Chemistry students' perception recorded a grand mean score of 57.8 and standard deviation of 27.31. This indicates that each item for the chemistry students' perception of the problem

Discussion

Chemistry teachers' perception of problems of teaching chemistry in senior schools. The study identified absenteeism of students from school, poor learning environment, inability to understand grammar, language, concept used in chemistry textbook, outdated textbooks, non-functional laboratory, lack of equipment and specimen in the laboratory to teach concepts and practical aspect of chemistry as challenges to teachers in the course of discharge of their duties. The findings of the study are in line with reports of (WAEC, 2022; Musengimana et al., 2021; Oladejo et al., 2021).

Also, chemistry teachers often struggle to provide hands-on experiences due to limited resources, time constraint and over loaded curriculum (Egolum and Okonkwo, 2022). Poor remuneration has led to teachers' poverty and further heightened issues in the teaching profession. This has posed so much financial incapability on the teachers, leading to transfer of aggression to students in the classroom, sometimes, and absenteeism among teachers, hence, contributing to inappropriate characteristics of teachers. Inadequate chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools contribute to much load of work on available teachers (Etebu & Amatari, 2020). This could prevent teachers from teaching all the topics in the scheme for the term and also give room for employment of non-professionals in the secondary schools.

The study also disapproved the following as not contributing to problems of teaching chemistry in senior secondary schools: chemistry teachers' attitude, many calculations in some topics in chemistry, time given to teach chemistry not enough, unprofessional chemistry teachers, some diagram, structures and concept used in chemistry textbook being difficult for students to understand. These implied that the above mentioned are not issues in teaching chemistry. This is in

of chemistry concept has affect the chemistry students' performance of chemistry negatively in senior schools in Ogbia Local Government Area. The findings also reveal that students see all the items to be the problem that affect their academic performance and that they find it difficult to understand chemistry concept.

disagreement with WAEC (2022) and (Nidup et al., 2021). The study also disapproved lack of infrastructure and modern facilities and instructional materials which aid learning. These implied that there are enough infrastructure, facilities and instructional materials in secondary schools. This is in disagreement with the study of Shoge & Kabiru (2024) which revealed that infrastructure, modern facilities and good use of instructional materials are not obtainable in some schools, hence, challenging students' academic achievement in science.

Students' perception of problem of learning chemistry in secondary schools. Having noted trend of students' poor academic achievement in chemistry, the study reported that the 20 items on the questionnaire are students' perception of problems of learning chemistry. Absenteeism of students from school, poor learning environment, Lack of equipment in the laboratory, Lack of specimens in laboratory, outdated chemistry textbooks and lack of infrastructure and modern facilities are militating against proper understanding of chemistry, thereby causing poor academic achievement in chemistry students. This is in line with the work of Casian, Mugo & Claire, 2021 and Naeem, Ali & Ahmad (2022). Some grammar, language, structures, concept and diagrams used in chemistry textbook is difficult for students to understand (WAEC, 2022). Grammar, language and terminology used in some chemistry textbooks often cause confusion to students. Calculations in chemistry has continued to be a challenge to students due to poor background in mathematics from primary and secondary schools. This is conformity with the study of Naeem, Ali & Ahmad (2022). Time allotted to teach chemistry is inadequate to explain, buttress and practicalize chemistry concept for better understanding.

Teacher factors cannot be over emphasized as regards to students' academic achievement in chemistry (Cleopas, 2020; Etebu & Amatari, 2020). Most times, transfer of aggression as a result of teachers' personal challenges is brought to the classroom and show cased as inappropriate teachers' attitude which is a hindrance to students' academic achievement in chemistry. Financial constraint as a result of poverty could contribute to absenteeism of teachers to classes as this bring about inability to cover the syllabus.

Conclusion

The findings of the study, teachers and students' perception of problems of teaching chemistry in senior schools have identified some difficulties why student misunderstand the concept of chemistry which might be due to inadequate and wrong use of teaching methods, absenteeism, attitude, inability to cover chemistry syllabus, difficult medium of instruction, language problem, abstract form of chemistry, mathematical calculations, among others which may affect student academic performance. The study established that modifying mode of instruction, language used, absenteeism, calculation, among others will help in improving the academic performance of students in chemistry and consequently help in addressing the difficulties and challenges in student encountered in learning and understanding the chemical concepts. The limitations of the study included that respondent's perception may be subjective, selected schools in Ogbia Local Government Area were used which limits generalization to a smaller scope and quantitative analysis alone was done excluding qualitative analysis which would have explained further the rationale behind students' perception.

Recommendation

Based on the following findings, the study suggested that

1. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use appropriate teaching methods with instructional materials to simplify the language of science, chemistry in particular, to the students.
2. Workshops and seminars should be organized periodically to train chemistry teachers for effectiveness and quality delivery.

3. Teachers welfare which is one of the why of absenteeism should be looked into in order to curb poor performance of chemistry students.

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